

VIKSIT BHARAT: 2047-STRATEGIES FOR GROWTH

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Abstract

Three times meal, Clean drinking water, Fresh air to breath, Good road, Work according to ability, good judiciary system, Electricity all the time, Rule of law and The person at the very bottom, in the last line of society, should receive everything they are entitled to. He should earn enough income to live his life with dignity. It means per capita income of the country should be good if not very high. Everyone in the nation must have a secure present and future, not even a secure future, but the future should be even brighter than the present. These are all characteristics of a happy nation. This is the dream that India has also seen. That is why the government has made plans and changed goals to achieve dreams. This is the aspiration for a developed India by 2047. (VIKSIT BHARAT-2047). By 2047, as the nation celebrates 100 years of freedom, every citizen should get everything they are entitled to.

Key Words: *Orange Economy, Viability Gap Funding, Capex*

Introduction

The vision of **Viksit Bharat @2047** represents India's ambitious roadmap to transform into a fully developed nation by the 100th anniversary of its independence. To bridge the gap from a developing to a developed status, India aims for a **\$30 trillion economy (30,000,000,000,000)** 3×10^{13} with an estimated per capita income of **\$18,000 to \$21,000**. However, to achieve this situation, our GDP growth rate should be 7-10% annually for the next 20 years.

Objective

To analyze the role of government policies and governance reform's for achieving developed-nation status by 2047.

The research paper is purely based on the available secondary data. Data is collected from various publications of the central government, state governments, various publications of international bodies and their subsidiary organizations, previous research paper, articles, magazines and the data available from authentic websites and published data available in open sources.

Present position of India

India has achieved notable progress being the Third-largest economy by Purchasing Power Parity (\$19trillion approx.) and Fourth-largest economy in terms of nominal GDP (\$4.18 trillion). But despite all of these India's Human

Development Index stands at approximately 0.685, placing it in the medium human development category and below the standards of advanced economies. India has recorded significant improvements in physical and digital infrastructure digital payment systems like Unified Payment System (UPI) handles 640+ millions transaction daily and internet connectivity have crossed the 100 crore milestone internet connection in country.

Role of Government

The government has identified four foundational "pillars" (demographic groups) essential to driving this growth:

- 1. Yuva (Youth):** Empowering the "X-factor" through skill development, innovation, and leadership opportunities. About Rs. 630 crores has been disbursed as the first installment for the chosen PM SHRI schools, More than 10,000 Atal Tinkering Labs nationwide and PM Kaushal- Vikas Yojana have up skilled millions.
- 2. Garib (Poor):** Aiming for **Zero Poverty** in Viksit Bharat 2047 is achieved through inclusive development, protecting the rights of weaker sections, empowering Divyangs (divyangjan) through specialised support mechanisms. and multi-dimensional empowerment.
- 3. Mahilayen (Women):** Targeting a **70% participation rate** of women in economic activities to

unlock untapped potential. Reservation of 33% of the seats in the Lok Sabha and in the state assemblies and the Nari Shakti Vandana Adhiniyam guaranteeing quotas to SC and ST women are promoting women's leadership.

- Annadata (Farmers): Modernizing agriculture to make India the "food basket of the world" Several schemes such as PM KISAN, Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana, Soil Health Cards, Kisan Credit Cards, PM-PRANAM scheme has been introduced to empower farmers with better resources

Key Strategies for Growth

Realizing the 2047 vision necessitates transformative reforms across several critical domains. Finance minister Nirmala Sitharaman in the budget 2026 highlighted the term "ORANGE ECONOMY".

Economic & Industrial Transformation

The prerequisite for achieving economic growth in a country is a favorable business environment. India, one of the World's fastest-developing countries, has the potential to surpass top leading countries in terms of business opportunities. The government has introduced several industry-friendly policies to enable ease of doing business and reduce cost of doing business through the manufacturing sector's contribution to **25% of GDP** by FY2047. These include Production Linked Incentive (PLI) schemes, Remission of Duties and Taxes on Exported Products (RoDTEP), PM Gati Shakti, India Industrial Landbank, the National Logistics Policy and the National Single Window System. Further, reduction in corporate taxes, financial market reforms, consolidation of public sector banks, enactment of four labour codes, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) policy reforms.

MSME Support

In India Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sector serves as a cornerstone for fostering socio-economic development. Bolstering Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises with enhanced credit access and digital tools to scale them into global competitors.

Table: Classification of MSMEs

Classification	Micro	Small	Medium
Manufacturing Enterprises and Enterprises rendering Services	Investment in Plant and Machinery or Equipment: Not more than Rs.1 crore and Annual Turnover ; not more than Rs. 5 crore	Investment in Plant and Machinery or Equipment: Not more than Rs.10 crore and Annual Turnover ; not more than Rs. 50 crore	Investment in Plant and Machinery or Equipment: Not more than Rs.50 crore and Annual Turnover ; not more than Rs. 250 crore

The MSME sector contributes significantly to India's total exports, accounting for approximately 49% of the

country's export earnings, highlighting its vital role in driving international trade, Share of MSMEs in India's GDP is 31.1 %. (ECONOMIC SURVEY 2025-26). A ₹10,000 crore SME Growth Fund in budget 2026-27 has been announced to support scaling up of high-performing enterprises. In addition, the Self-Reliant India Fund receives an additional ₹2,000 crore to ensure continued access to risk capital for micro enterprises.

Physical Infrastructure

Supply chain reliability is at the core of logistics performance from point of origin to point of consumption. Logistics ensure that products reach consumers for final consumption timely and without spoilage. The government has been swiftly adopting and implementing reforms to rationalise and increase efficiency of logistics. In 2021, the Government of India launched the PM GatiShakti National Master Plan (PMGS-NMP) towards a coordinated approach, leveraging technology, for infrastructure planning and development. To boost the ease of doing business the National Logistics Policy (NLP) was launched in 2022. The NLP thus aims to promote seamless movement of goods and enhance the competitiveness of Indian industries. Seven high-speed rail corridors have been announced in budget 2026-27 to connect major economic and urban centre. These corridors (Mumbai-Pune, Pune-Hyderabad, Hyderabad-Bengaluru, Hyderabad-Chennai, Chennai-Bengaluru, Delhi-Varanasi, and Varanasi-Siliguri) are expected to reduce travel time, improve regional connectivity, and support economic integration. Public capital expenditure (capex) has been increased from 11.2 lakh crore to ₹12.2 lakh crore in FY 2026-27.

Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI): In this cyber age the World has now become a global village, where everyone is connected with each other. India currently stands at the 40th rank (2023) in the Government AI Readiness Index, which was 51 in 2021. It is projected that India will be among the Top 20 Countries by 2030, among the Top 10 Countries by 2040 and among the Top 5 Countries by 2047.

Human Capital Development

Education Reform: Education strengthens institutions, ignites innovation and builds resilient communities. A well-educated, technically-qualified workforce enhances productivity, which is crucial for sustained economic growth. Aligning with the **National Education Policy (NEP) 2020** to achieve **100% literacy** and focus on industry-ready vocational training In FY 2026-27 five University Townships are planned near major industrial and logistics corridors to improve linkages between academia and industry and one girls' hostel will be established in every district through viability gap funding.

Healthcare for All: Strengthening public health systems through the **Ayushman Bharat** initiative to increase life expectancy and ensure universal access to affordable care. The life expectancy has increased from 63 years in the year 2000 to 67 years in 2021. It is projected that life expectancy at birth will grow to 74 years by 2030 and 84

to 2047. In FY 2026-27 the budget proposes the establishment of five Regional Medical Hubs to position India as a destination for medical services. Three new All India Institutes of Ayurveda are proposed to strengthen traditional medicine systems.

Challenges

The path towards Viksit Bharat is marked by several structural and systemic challenges. Persistent income inequality, regional disparities, Employment generation poses a significant concern, as the expanding workforce—especially the youth—faces limited access to productive and formal employment opportunities, social challenges further impede progress.

Recommendations and Conclusion

Government should implement tax policies that decrease the tax burden on lower-income groups and to promote regional prosperity government should prioritize investment in under developed areas. The problem of unemployment will be solved by promoting MSMEs, Startup and entrepreneur. Proper infrastructure, planning, active participation from government, industry, civil society and most importantly from common people is pre requisite for Viksit Bharat.

Projections are that by 2047 India will among top 5 countries. The efforts of Government reflects that the India is determined to transform itself into a developed economy (Viksit Bharat) by 2047. The study indicates that India has made marvelous progress in areas such as economic growth, infrastructure development, institutional reforms, social welfare coverage, and digital expansion.

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